

Abortion

The research will be performed on the topic of Abortion. The following section discusses a brief outline of the research paper.

Definition and Explanation

Abortion pertains to the expulsion or removal of the embryo or fetus from the uterus thus, annihilating the pregnancy before it is suitable. It can either be induced on purpose, or happen spontaneously, and the condition is generally known as a miscarriage. These terms usually refers to the abortion of a human pregnancy. The process of abortion may be carried in safe or unsafe manners (Sedgh, et. al., 2012). The concept of induced abortion is made possible by numerous processes which also include the utilization of sharpened tools, herbal abortifacients, the usage of physical trauma, and other conventional procedures. The modern medicine uses the surgical and medications methods to perform abortion to the human pregnancy. There may be the substantial variations in the prevalence, legality, religious and cultural status of abortion across the globe.

History

The concept of induced abortion dates back to the heterogeneous civilizations as Ancient Egypt, China under Shennong, and the Roman Empire in the time of Juvenal (c. 200 CE). There are many evidences which suggest that the pregnancies were terminated with the help of various methods. These methods included the use of sharpened implements, the management of abortifacients herbs, the application of abdominal pressure, and various other methods.

Types

There are different types of abortions as follows:

Induced

On an average, around 205 million pregnancies take place across the world every year. More than one third of the abortions are unintentional, while around a fifth is the induced abortion (Sedgh, et. al. 2007).

Spontaneous

Miscarriage, or the spontaneous abortion, refers to the accidental removal of the fetus or embryo before the gestation reaches its 24th week. However, the stillbirths and premature births are usually not acknowledged as miscarriages though these terms are sometimes used interchangeably. The most frequent reason for the spontaneous abortion in the first trimester is usually the abnormalities of chromosomes in the fetus or embryo, and these accounts for the minimum of 50% of observed early pregnancy losses.

Induction Methods

There are two methods of inducing an abortion:

Medical

The abortifacients pharmaceuticals induce the medical abortions and these take form of a substitute abortion process with the availability of prostaglandin analogs and the antiprogesterone mifepristone.

Surgical

This method is a vacuum aspiration abortion which is performed at the gestational age of eight weeks, or in other words, six weeks after fertilization. The most commonly used methods of induced abortion are the vacuum aspiration or suction-aspiration, up to the gestation of 15 weeks. The manual vacuum aspiration (MVA) entails eliminating the embryo or fetus, membranes, and the placenta through suction by utilizing the manual syringe. On the other hand, the electric vacuum aspiration (EVA) is performed using an electric pump. Sometimes, abortion is performed by causing pain to the abdomen.

Society and Culture

There has been a big debate, activism, and controversy over the induced abortion. The individuals' opinions regarding abortion may relate to his/her legal, ethical, family and cultural values, and may be elaborated upon as the blend of beliefs regarding the morality of abortion. The modern laws and legislation with respect to abortion involve heterogeneous views. The right to liberty, right to life, the right to reproductive health, and the right to security of person are the

significant human rights issues which are generally utilized as the justification for the absence or existence of abortion controlling laws.

Works Cited

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Appendix